

MATRIX MODELING IN ARITHMETIC WITH C++ LANGUAGE BASED ON CODE-BLOCK

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Abstrak

Mathematics is the study of things such as magnitude, structure and change. Mathematicians assemble and use various patterns. Mathematics is divided into two namely basic mathematics and discrete mathematics, in basic mathematics there are several kinds of material one of which is about matrix. Matrix is a set of numbers arranged in rows and columns and placed in ordinary brackets or square brackets.

I. Introduction

1.1 Background

Mathematics comes from the Latin language *manthanein* or *Mathema* which means “learning learning things”. While mathematics in Dutch is known as *wiskunde* which means “exact science”. So in general it can be interpreted that mathematics is an exact science that is concerned with reasoning.

The lack of students' understanding of mathematical concepts raises difficulties in solving mathematical problems not only caused by the students themselves, but is also supported by the inability of teachers to create situations that can make students interested in mathematical learning.

Here we will help the process of learning mathematics to be more easily understood by students by explaining the material with pictures. We will try to explain matrix material using C++ based on CODE-BLOCK.

1.2 Formulation of the problem

Based on the journal title above that most students do like mathematics especially matrix material.

1.3 Aim

A. As a form implementation of algorithmic and programming courses

B. As a semester final assignment for one of the basic algorithmic and programming courses

C. As a mathematics learning media especially matrix material in the form of programs

1.4 Benefits

We hope that this matrix program can facilitate the mathematics learning process in matrix material, so that students are more interested and easier to understand the material.

II. Literature review

2.1 Theoretical basis

A matrix is a group arrangement of numbers in a rectangular array arranged according to rows and columns and placed between two parentheses. The parentheses used to flank the arrangement of the matrix members can be either regular brackets or square brackets. Every number in a matrix is called a matrix element. A collection of elements arranged horizontally is called a row, while a collection of elements arranged vertically is called a column (Ashar Fajar ; 2015)

Algorithm is a special method that is appropriate and consist of a series of steps that are structured and written mathematically, which will be done to solve a problem with the help of a computer. So based on this definition, it can be said that the algorithm is a step in solving a problem that produces a solution in the form of a computer program. (Andy Prasetyo ; 2018)

In mathematics and computer science, algorithms are sequences or steps for calculation or to solve a problem written sequentially. So, programming algorithms are sequences or steps to solve computer programming problems. (Abidin RIswa ; 2016)

C++ is a programming language that has the properties of object-oriented programming. To solve the problem, C++ takes the first step by explaining classes that are child classes that were made before as an abstraction of physical object. The class contains the state of objects, members and abilities from the object, after several classes are made then the problem is solved by class. C language is a procedural programming language that allows us to make procedures to solve a problem. C++ programming language is an object-oriented programming language (Trisasi Mekar 2015)

Code-Block is a free software, non-profit, open sources and cross platform integrated development environment program. Programs witten in C++ along with Widgets for

their GUI can be used in conjunction with various compilers, for example GCC and Visual C++.(Awaliyah Dhara Ulfah 2018)

2.2 Related research

There are several studies on matrix modeling algorithms, as follows :

Zulfikar, Alif Akhmad. "Program C Matriks". 15 Januari 2017.

Matrix programs can be made using language C, with looping commands like For, While, and Do-While. All three commands can be applied to loop in the looping.

Novitasari, Candra. "Pengertian Pemrograman Secara Lengkap". 4 December 2017.

Programming is the process of writing, fixing errors (bugs) and testing a program. Programming includes codes written in various programming languages.

The purpose of programming is to create a system that is interconnected and includes code presented by the programmer. There are also those who call programming is art that is created for something useful in form of a system.

III. Research methods

The stages in this study are as follows :

- a) Data collection
- b) Preliminary data processing
- c) Grouping
- d) The proposed method stage
- e) Model experiment and testing
- f) Research evaluation and validation

The method proposed in this study is MATRIX MODELING IN ARITHMETIC WITH C++ LANGUAGE BASED ON CODE-BLOCK

Following the steps in this research :

1. Show name, class, and nim with the command cout
2. Specify the variables that we will in the program
3. Determine the numbers of columns and matrix lines
4. Use the looping function for
5. Enter the row and column numbers with the command cin

Flowchart Program

```

main.cpp x
1
2 #include<iostream>
3 #include<conio.h>
4 #include<iomanip>
5 using namespace std;
6 main()
7 {
8     cout<<endl;
9     cout<<" Nama      : Aenul Azmi "<<endl;
10    cout<<" Kelas       : 1 C "<<endl;
11    cout<<" Mata Kuliah  : Algoritma & Pemrograman "<<endl<<endl;
12
13    int a[3][3],b[3][3],c[3][3],i,j,k;
14
15    cout<<" Matriks 3 x 3 :";
16    cout<<endl;
17    for(i=0;i<3;i++){
18    for(j=0;j<3;j++){
19
20        cout<<" Input Baris "<<(i+1)<<" , Kolom "<<(j+1)<<" = ";
21
22        cin>>a[i][j];}
23        cout<<endl;}
24
25    cout<<" Matriks 3 x 3 = "<<endl<<endl;
26
27    for(i=0;i<3;i++){
28    for(j=0;j<3;j++){
29        cout<<setw(4)<<a[i][j];}
30        cout<<endl<<endl;}
31    getch ();
32    }
33

```

Picture 3.1 Source Code Opening Program

```

13    int a[3][3],b[3][3],c[3][3],i,j,k;
14
15    cout<<" Matriks 3 x 3 :";
16    cout<<endl;
17    for(i=0;i<3;i++){
18    for(j=0;j<3;j++){
19
20        cout<<" Input Baris "<<(i+1)<<" , Kolom "<<(j+1)<<" = ";
21
22        cin>>a[i][j];}
23        cout<<endl;}
24
25    cout<<" Matriks 3 x 3 = "<<endl<<endl;
26
27    for(i=0;i<3;i++){
28    for(j=0;j<3;j++){
29        cout<<setw(4)<<a[i][j];}

```

Picture 3.2 Source Code Calculation Program

D:\c++\matriks\bin\Debug\matriks.exe

```
Nama      : Aenul Azmi
Kelas   : 1 C
Mata Kuliah : Algoritma & Pemrograman

Matriks 3 x 3 :
Input Baris 1 , Kolom 1 =
```

Picture 3.3 Indentify Program

Select D:\c++\matriks\bin\Debug\matriks.exe

```
Nama      : Aenul Azmi
Kelas   : 1 C
Mata Kuliah : Algoritma & Pemrograman

Matriks 3 x 3 :
Input Baris 1 , Kolom 1 = 3
Input Baris 1 , Kolom 2 = 2
Input Baris 1 , Kolom 3 = 4

Input Baris 2 , Kolom 1 = 1
Input Baris 2 , Kolom 2 = 3
Input Baris 2 , Kolom 3 = 2

Input Baris 3 , Kolom 1 = 3
Input Baris 3 , Kolom 2 = 2
Input Baris 3 , Kolom 3 = 1

Matriks 3 x 3 =

 3  2  4
 1  3  2
 3  2  1

Process returned 0 (0x0)   execution time : 138.985 s
Press any key to continue.
█
```

Picture 3.4 Result On Console Program

IV. Conclusions and Recommendations

From the above paper we can conclude that basically in everyday life we often deal with problems that if we trace it turns out to be a mathematical problem. In other words we always come into contact with problems related to mathematics whether we realize it or not. To be easily understood, the problem is changed into language or mathematical equations so that the problem is easier to solve. But sometimes a problem often contains more than two equations and several variables, so we have difficulty finding relationships between the variables.

A matrix is a set of numbers arranged in rows and rectangular columns. The matrix is characterized by constituent elements flanked by square brackets [] or ordinary parentheses (). The size of a matrix is expressed in units of order, namely the number of rows and columns in the matrix.

Hopefully the writer and reader can know and understand this matrix material especially its application using CODE-BLOCK and hopefully this program about matrix material can be useful for the learning process. If there are errors in writing this paper the author expects criticism or suggestions from readers.

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